

BLUEMISSION AA

Building a coordination hub to support the mission
implementation in the *Atlantic and Arctic Basin*

PROJECT WEBSITE AND SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS

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1. Introduction

The Website and Social Media Accounts deliverable is part of the Task 6.4 Communication and Outreach under Work Package 6, led by the AD AIR Centre. This deliverable (D6.7) is a brief report describing the different communication channels that we will use to promote the project.

2. Website

A dedicated and regularly updated website serves as a reference platform for BlueMissionAA' external online communication. The website is the primary asset for promoting the project activities and results to all audiences, providing comprehensive information about BlueMissionAA, its objectives and achievements, the consortium, news, events, newsletters, press announcements, and other relevant information. The website has been launched and can be accessed at www.bluemissionaa.eu.

3. Social Media Accounts

BlueMissionAA social media will raise awareness to the project, its success stories, common topics of interest, news, events, and publications. Currently, the most popular social media includes Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Mastodon, Twitter, and YouTube. We have set up and will use these accounts to report on project achievements, events, as well as to draw attention to relevant news and activities from Atlantic and Arctic basins lighthouses. The six social media accounts are shown below.

3.1 Facebook

BlueMissionAA's facebook account can be accessed here:
www.facebook.com/bluemotionaa.

3.2 Instagram

BlueMissionAA's Instagram account can be accessed here:
www.instagram.com/bluemissionaa/.

3.3 LinkedIn

BlueMissionAA's LinkedIn account can be accessed here:
www.linkedin.com/company/bluemissionaa.

3.4 Mastodon

BlueMissionAA's Mastodon account can be accessed here:

<https://ohai.social/@bluemissionaa>.

3.5 Twitter

BlueMissionAA's Twitter account can be accessed here:

<https://twitter.com/bluemissionaa>.

3.6 YouTube Channel

BlueMissionAA's YouTube Channel account can be accessed here:

www.youtube.com/@bluemissionaa.

The screenshot shows the YouTube channel page for BlueMissionAA. The channel name is BlueMissionAA with the handle @bluemissionaa. The channel is described as a coordination hub for the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 in the Atlantic & Arctic basins. The description mentions 15 partners and their focus on marine and coastal ecosystems. The channel was joined on Nov 30, 2022. The page includes a search bar, a subscribe button, and navigation tabs for Home, Playlists, Channels, and About.

BlueMissionAA
@bluemissionaa

Subscribe

HOME **PLAYLISTS** **CHANNELS** **ABOUT**

Description

BlueMissionAA is the coordination hub that will support the implementation of the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 in the Atlantic & Arctic basins. It will focus on restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems and increased climate resilience. The consortium is comprised of 15 partners who have worked extensively in the Atlantic and Arctic basin over the years. They combine the benefits of a comprehensive geographical coverage with an evenly balanced mixture of unique capabilities, knowledge and access to relevant stakeholder and citizen networks needed to pursue the objectives of the project.

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Stats

Joined Nov 30, 2022

2023